

TRANSNATURE

Policy Recommendations: Baltic to Barents

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Introduction

Transboundary cooperation in the field of biodiversity protection is a relatively understudied governance mechanism in Europe. The project “TRANSNATURE – TRANSboundary governance models of biodiversity protection: case studies for greater protection of NATURal resources in Europe” aims to fill this gap by focusing on four case studies across Europe. As part of the TRANSNATURE project, this report introduces seven policy recommendations that suggest ways to improve current mechanisms for transboundary cooperation on biodiversity protection between Finland and Sweden, and between Finland and Norway, and ultimately to strengthen biodiversity conservation and sustainable development in Northern Europe.

The suggested policy recommendations draw extensively from inputs on challenges and visions collected during fieldwork conducted between June and November 2024 (21 interviews and one focus group meeting). The first draft of the policy recommendations was discussed in an online stakeholder meeting held on 31 October 2025 and, based on the feedback received, the final set of policy recommendations was completed. The main categories of stakeholders involved were local, regional and national authorities, international organisations, research institutes, and representatives of local communities and Indigenous Peoples.

More specifically, the policy recommendations outlined in this report focus on the case study entitled *Baltic to Barents*, which covers three examples of transboundary cooperation on biodiversity protection in the border areas of Finland-Sweden and Finland-Norway. These examples include:

- 1) Transboundary cooperation between Finland and Sweden regarding the legally binding Agreement Concerning Transboundary Rivers (2010) between the two countries covering the border rivers Tornionjoki, Muoniojoki and Könkämäeno along with their tributary rivers, and a small part of the Bothnian Bay. It establishes the Finnish-Swedish Transboundary Rivers Commission as a cooperation body.
- 2) Transboundary cooperation between Finland and Norway regarding the Haldi Transboundary Area, a cooperative area established in 2020 through a Cooperation Agreement, comprising the Käsivarsi Wilderness Area (Finland) and the Reisa National Park and Ráisduottarháldi Landscape Conservation Area (Norway).
- 3) Cooperation between Finland and Norway regarding the Pasvik-Inari Transboundary Area, based on a new bilateral agreement between nature protection area management bodies in Finland and Norway, signed in May 2025. Originally, this transboundary cooperation was called the Pasvik-Inari Trilateral Park and covered a continuous area including the Vätsäri Wilderness Area (Finland), the Lake Inari Natura2000 site, the Øvre Pasvik National Park (Norway), the Øvre Pasvik Landscape Protection Area (Norway), the Pasvik Nature Reserve (Norway) and the Pasvik Zapovednik (Russia). Trilateral cooperation ended after Russia’s full-scale invasion of Ukraine in 2022.

Figure. Three examples of transboundary biodiversity protection in the northern areas of Finland, Norway, and Sweden (Arto Vitikka, Arctic Centre, University of Lapland. Border data: Runfola, D. et al. (2020) *geoBoundaries: A global database of political administrative boundaries*. PLoS ONE 15(4): e0231866. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0231866>; Arctic Indigenous languages and revitalization: an online educational resource (2024). Map and dataset of areas where languages are spoken (version 1.1) <https://arctic-indigenous-languages-uito.hub.arcgis.com> [data set]).

Policy Recommendation 1

Establish a formal participatory consultation mechanism to increase the level of public participation

Main problem: Equal public participation by local communities is not always guaranteed in transboundary biodiversity governance.

Addressees: local authorities, national authorities.

Recommendation:

Transboundary biodiversity governance should include a formal participatory and consultation mechanism established at the transboundary level to ensure equal participation of all stakeholder groups and local citizens from all participating states.

While the equal consultation of local communities and peoples is guaranteed in cooperation related to border rivers between Finland and Sweden, through the provisions of the legally binding Transboundary River Agreement (e.g., Art. 9 and 13), this is not automatically the case for cooperation between Norway and Finland regarding the Håldi TBA and the Pasvik-Inari Transboundary Area. In these mechanisms, the inclusion of local communities is valued and pursued, but not formalized through transboundary cooperation agreements. Accordingly, there is an imbalance in the representation and participation of local communities, which could be avoided through formally established consultation and participation mechanisms at the cross-border level. In addition, the views of local and regional participants should also be included in decisions as comprehensively as possible.

Added value: Increased efficiency in biodiversity governance and representativity would broaden the consensus base, and the harmonisation of the level of participation across countries would create equal opportunities for local communities.

Policy Recommendation 2

Flexible transboundary governance mechanisms allow for adaptation to changing circumstances

Main problem: Rigid governance mechanisms cannot adapt to changing circumstances, making transboundary biodiversity cooperation virtually impossible when unexpected challenges emerge.

Addressees: National and local authorities and politicians; transboundary cooperation bodies.

Recommendation: Governance mechanisms and practices for transboundary biodiversity protection must be flexible enough to allow for adaptation to the specific context and needs of the area, population, nature, and biodiversity, including consideration of relevant activities within and around the area.

When investigating the different examples and modes of transboundary governance between Finland and Sweden, as well as between Finland and Norway, it becomes clear that adaptation and flexibility in the governance mechanism and cooperation efforts allow for adaptation to emerging challenges. This is especially evident in the examples of cooperation between Finland and Norway, as they are based on non-legally binding cooperation agreements.* Leaving and providing room for flexibility within the cooperation mechanism allows participating states and stakeholders to adapt and adjust conservation efforts to the needs of the area, people, nature, and biodiversity, while keeping relevant activities that have an impact on these aspects in mind.

Added value: Different modes of governance and context-specific transboundary cooperation mechanisms could enhance biodiversity conservation efforts.

* In the example of the Pasvik-Inari Transboundary Area, which included cooperation with Russia before it invaded Ukraine in 2022, cooperation between Norway and Finland was able to continue without any difficulties. However, other mechanisms/bodies for transboundary environmental cooperation that do not fall within the scope of this project were unable to continue after the invasion without Russia, due to their legally binding nature and the specifics of their functioning. These examples include the Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission – also known as the Helsinki Commission (HELCOM) – based on a legally-binding agreement with decision-making through consensus, which was paralysed after Russia's full-scale attack on Ukraine.

Policy Recommendation 3

Consistent funding is needed to guarantee effective transboundary biodiversity governance and equal public participation

Main problem: There are insufficient permanent funding mechanisms for transboundary biodiversity governance.

Addressees: National authorities

Recommendation: Formal, consistent funding mechanisms and cooperation bodies at a transboundary level would allow for equal participation of stakeholders, strengthen cooperation, and support common objectives.

Funding is a determining factor for transboundary cooperation, as it allows for long-term conservation efforts. Of all the examples in the case study, only the Finnish-Swedish Transboundary River Commission has a formalised and permanent funding structure provided by the national budgets of Finland and Sweden, covering the expenses of the office and its work process, including participation, consultation, and information sharing, as well as some expenses of the Commission members. Although (non-legally binding) transboundary cooperation between Norway and Finland also comprises a transboundary funding mechanism, it remains largely dependent on funding generated at a national level. In the case of Norway, this comprises an annual budget provided by the state, in addition to external funding sources (e.g., INTERREG). In the case of Finland, funding is mainly generated through external funding mechanisms that are applied and awarded competitively, such as EU projects or INTERREG. However, funds provided by the state may also be allocated to secure basic cooperation tasks (e.g., funds for an annual meeting). Research has shown that some stakeholders, such as civil society, municipality representatives, Indigenous Peoples, and young people, could be excluded from conversations, actions, and access to full information on transboundary conservation efforts if no funding is allocated to ensure their formal participation. Additionally, national funding sources could be highly unbalanced between different partners, as one country may allocate more resources to nature conservation efforts than other countries involved.

Added value: A formalised and permanent funding structure would make the long-term development of transboundary conservation possible.

Policy Recommendation 4

Indigenous people's political representation and participation in biodiversity governance must be ensured

Main problem: Indigenous rights are not implemented or enforced (e.g., through the adoption of ILO169) equally across the Sámi Homeland. This may prevent or hinder equal representation and thus limit the participation of Indigenous stakeholders in the governance of biodiversity conservation in transboundary areas located in the Sámi Homeland, such as the Hálđi Transboundary Area and the Pasvik-Inari Transboundary Area.

Addressees: National authorities.

Recommendation: The different countries involved in the transboundary conservation area should individually and jointly work towards incorporating similar mechanisms that ensure the participation of Indigenous peoples in transboundary biodiversity governance. This could involve the transboundary implementation of a functional model that is already in place in Norway (e.g., in the case of the Norwegian representative for the Park Board nominated by the *Sámediggi* [Sámi Parliament]) or the development of a new mechanism to ensure the participation of Indigenous representatives in Sápmi, the Sámi Homeland.

Differences in the application of international regulations to national legislation impact the participation of Indigenous representatives in transboundary cooperation, if there is no transboundary mechanism in place to ensure equal participation. This can be seen in reference to ILO Convention 169 concerning Indigenous and Tribal Peoples in Independent Countries. The Convention has been ratified by Norway (Finnmark Act 2005 [LOV-2005-06-17-85]), but its ratification is still being debated in both Sweden and Finland. The effects of ILO 169 are evident in the fact that Norway has a stronger legal foundation for the consultation and inclusion of Indigenous Peoples compared to Sweden and Finland. While all three countries acknowledge the rights of Indigenous Peoples and the importance of meaningful engagement, the case study illustrates a notable difference in practice. In Norway, national legislation ensures that Indigenous Peoples are automatically included or represented in cooperative bodies. In contrast, in Finland and Sweden, there is no automatic institutionalised consideration for the consultation or inclusion of Indigenous Peoples, even though the transboundary areas, such as Hálđi and the Pasvik-Inari, by the Finnish-Norwegian border, are fully located in the Sámi Homeland. In addition to ILO Convention No. 169, the case study also illustrates differences in approaches to biodiversity conservation governance between Finland and a Schengen country (Sweden) and Finland and a non-Schengen country (Norway). These examples show how different the experiences, functioning, and effectiveness of governance can be with such different legal frameworks in place.

Added value: Greater democratic representation of Indigenous Peoples in the governance process, while also increasing the efficacy of transboundary governance.

Policy Recommendation 5

The cumulative transnational environmental impacts of socio-economic activities must be assessed

Main problem: A large number of green transition investments, such as wind power and mining, are planned in northern Europe. Although these are likely to have major cross-border environmental impacts, no joint environmental impact assessments of the cumulative effects of all planned investments have been undertaken. For example, an environmental impact assessment focusing on new investments in the Baltic Sea region does not comprehensively consider the cumulative impacts of all planned investments. This undermines future efforts to protect biodiversity in the transboundary area.

Addressees: Transboundary cooperation bodies; national authorities; technical experts/environmental consulting firms.

Recommendation: Procedures for environmental impact assessments (EIAs) should be strengthened to take account of cumulative impacts at transboundary level, including all planned investments impacting biodiversity in a transboundary area. Particularly, in the Baltic Sea region, the total cumulative environmental impact of all socio-economic projects should be evaluated and monitored through special maritime planning for the Baltic Sea at regional level.

Countries engaged in transboundary cooperation for biodiversity conservation should ensure that they align with or fully implement the provisions of the 1994 Espoo Convention on EIAs in a transboundary context. The environmental impacts of local economic activities often extend beyond national borders, damaging local ecosystems and species in general (e.g., air and water pollution caused by a local nickel mine emitting greenhouse gases and discharging toxin-rich wastewater). However, traditionally, EIAs focus on a specific activity, often disregarding other environmental impacts from adjacent economic activities, which add to the pressure on the ecosystem and its biodiversity. While some countries mandate the consideration of cumulative impacts in EIAs (e.g., Norway), others lack procedures for assessing cumulative impacts (e.g., Finland and Sweden). In accordance with Article 8, parties may enter into bilateral or multilateral agreements to fulfil their obligations under the Espoo Convention. These may include the harmonisation of policies and measures for the protection of the environment, the comprehensive application of EIAs (Annex VI.2(c) of the Espoo Convention), as well as the implementation, where appropriate, of joint monitoring programmes or the harmonisation of methods to streamline the data obtained (Annex VI.2(g) of the Espoo Convention). Strengthening these efforts is important in order to adequately consider cumulative impacts at a transboundary level and enhance multilateralism and cooperation among transboundary actors.

Added value: Stronger multilateralism between cooperating States and a more realistic assessment of the environmental impacts of economic activities provide a solid basis for enhanced biodiversity protection in the future.

Policy Recommendation 6

More knowledge is needed concerning the cumulative impacts of offshore wind power on biodiversity in the Baltic Sea region

Main problem: There is insufficient scientific knowledge concerning the cumulative impacts of green transition investments, such as offshore wind power, on biodiversity in the Baltic Sea region in general and on migratory species in particular.

Addressees: Research community; national and local authorities; energy transition investors/institutions.

Recommendation: Before large-scale offshore wind power is utilised, more research is needed on its cumulative effects on migratory species. Prospective studies are needed, for example, on how the growing number of wind farms in the Baltic Sea would cumulatively affect nocturnal bats and migratory fish during their migratory period across the sea and on their way back to their home river to breed.

In addition to the positive effects on climate change mitigation, offshore wind power has negative implications for ecosystems during the construction, operation, and decommissioning phases. These impacts, inter alia, on birds, fish, marine mammals, and bats include mortality from collision, displacement from breeding or nesting areas, disruption of migration corridors, barrier/avoidance effects on movement, acoustic and electromagnetic disturbances, as well as changes in food supply and habitat. Offshore wind power will have a broad impact across the entire Baltic Sea region, as it is a growing source of electricity and is in line with the EU Renewable Energy Directive. The Tornionjoki river basin, located on the Finland–Sweden border, produces most of Europe’s wild salmon and is also home to other migratory species, such as whitefish and trout. These fish are born in the tributaries, migrate to the Baltic Sea and return after a few years to spawn. The cumulative effects of offshore wind power affect many species, including migratory fish, which could find their return to their spawning areas impeded.

Added value: Sufficient and diverse research on the impacts of the green transition helps to make more sustainable decisions.

Policy Recommendation 7

Cross-border planning and management procedures should be developed

Main problem: Despite the growing number of green transition activities in northern Europe related, for example, to wind power and mining, no transnational coordination of these activities takes place. Instead, socio-economic activities and nature conservation are subject to the national jurisdiction of each state participating in transboundary cooperation for biodiversity protection. This hinders, to some extent, joint work for biodiversity protection in the transboundary area.

Addressees: National and local authorities; transboundary governance bodies/mechanisms.

Recommendation: Transnational cooperation, discussion and planning, such as regarding joint border river management, are important for cross-border biodiversity protection. Special joint maritime planning should also be developed among the Baltic Sea states. Moreover, further cross-border planning and management procedures and other cooperation tools should be developed so that, where necessary, deeper transnational cooperation on biodiversity protection is possible. New needs are likely to arise as a result of climate change and new technological developments. This may require changes to the national legislation of the respective States.

Added value: Extended opportunities for joint stewardship of the border region can lead to more effective management and protection of nature in the transboundary area, and contribute to a more sustainable green transition on an environmental, cultural, economic, political, and social scale.